

N-substituted Benzohydroxamic acids as ligands. Part I. Sodium N-Benzoyl N-*p*-hydroxylaminobenzenesulphonate (BPAHS)

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In this laboratory some N-acyl N-phenyl hydroxylamines¹⁻³ have been prepared. They are found to yield water insoluble chelates with many metal ions. Such ligands may be more useful for spectrophotometric studies and as masking agents, if the metal chelates are made water soluble. With this in view the compound sodium N-benzoyl N-*p*-hydroxylaminobenzenesulphonate (BPAHS) has been synthesised. It forms water soluble complexes with Fe(III), Ti(IV), Cu(II), Ni(II) and U(VI).

The present communication consists of a study of Fe(III) and U(VI) complexes in solution. It has been observed that absorption peaks are shifted towards lower wavelengths in each case on raising pH of the solutions—showing the formation of different complexes. So to find out their composition by the application of Job's method of continuous variation⁴, has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of sodium N-benzoyl N *p*-hydroxylaminobenzenesulphonate

Sodium *p*-nitrobenzenesulphonate (0.12 mole) was converted to sodium *p*-hydroxylaminobenzenesulphonate following the usual method by reduction with zinc dust in presence of NH₄Cl. After filtration the solution containing sodium *p*-hydroxylaminobenzenesulphonate was allowed to condense with benzoyl chloride (0.1 mole) with subsequent neutralisation of acid by adding small amounts of sodium bicarbonate⁵. The pH of the solution was then made upto ≈ 4 by HCl; and concentrated in a vacuum desiccator over H₂SO₄ when crystals separated. The compound was purified by recrystallisation from rectified spirit. It was then air dried and analysed. [Found: N = 4.52, Na = 7.39; Calc: N = 4.44, Na = 7.30%].

It is soluble in water and sparingly so in rectified spirit. It forms water soluble chelates with many metal ions.

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All other reagents used were either A.R. quality or properly purified. Optical densities were measured with a spectrophotometer (UVISPEK) using 1 cm. quartz cell against water as blank. pH was measured with Cambridge pH meter (portable type).

In studying the composition of the complexes of Fe(III) and U(VI) by Job's method, first spectral curves were drawn in each case at different pH values. Regarding Fe(III) complexes, 3 ml of 0.003 M $FeCl_3$ solution and 9 ml equimolecular ligand solution were taken in each of a number of 25 ml measuring flasks and after adjusting to desired pH values, the volumes were made upto the mark. Optical densities of these solutions were measured at different wavelengths against water as blank. Data are presented graphically by plotting optical densities against corresponding wavelengths (Fig. 1). The same was repeated using

Fig. 1 Spectral curves for Fe(III) chelates
 I, $pH = 0.84$; II, $pH = 1.22$; III, $pH = 2.22$;
 IV, $pH = 2.52$; V, $pH = 3.30$.

0.03 M uranyl nitrate and equimolecular ligand solutions (Fig. 2). From the curves, wavelengths at different pH values were chosen to study the composition by Job's method of continuous variation. For the purpose of finding out the composition, a number of 25 ml measuring flasks were taken and two different equimolecular solutions of Fe(III) and the ligand prepared separately, were mixed accordingly. The volumes were made upto the mark, after adjusting pH values either with HCl and/or acetic acid and sodium acetate. The optical densities of these solutions were measured at the selected wavelengths against water. The

differences of optical densities between the observed values and the calculated values if there be no complex formation, were plotted against corresponding composition. The same procedure was adopted to find out the composition of U(VI) complexes using two different equimolecular solutions of uranyl nitrate and the ligand (BPAHS). The pH values were adjusted with dilute HCl and/or NH_4OH solutions.

Fig: 2 Spectral curves for U(VI) chelates
I, $pH = 3.90$; II, $pH = 4.58$; III, $pH = 5.26$

RESULTS

By Job's method of continuous variation, the existence of three different complexes of Fe(III) and BPAHS has been indicated. The purple complex (1 : 1) at $\lambda = 500 m\mu$ and $pH = 0.84$, the red complex (1 : 2) at $\lambda = 495 m\mu$ and $pH = 2.52$ and the orange-red complex (1 : 3) at $\lambda = 480 m\mu$ and $pH = 3.30$, have been observed. Regarding U(VI) and BPAHS the formation of two complexes—orange-red one (1 : 1) at $\lambda = 475 m\mu$ and $pH = 3.90$ and orange one (1 : 2) at $\lambda = 460 m\mu$ and $pH = 5.26$ —has been found.

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